

EDUCATIONAL CHANGE AMIDST COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND THE TEACHERS' WELL-BEING: INPUT FOR FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

JAN MARIE TRIX CAPONPON PUNZALAN

magsamboljanmarietrix@gmail.com

ORCID Number: 00000—0003-1454-2452

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to find out the significant relationship between the educational change amidst COVID-19 and the well-being of the teachers at Calauan District. This study utilized the descriptive-correlation type of research. The respondents are composed of the one hundred fifty-six (156) public elementary school teacher in Calauan District for the school year 2020-2021 and the total enumeration was employed in selecting the respondents of the study. The study found that the respondents perceived educational change to teacher's well-being in terms of physical health found to be significantly related. However, mental health found no significant relationship to educational change. Based on the above findings the following recommendations are set forth: The teachers may continue using blended learning when normal schooling starts since modular distance learning taught students the value of self-reliance, independence and being responsible in their studies which may help them minimize the bulk of workloads in everyday teaching if the school permit. Despite the "no significant" relationship was found between the educational change and well-being in terms of mental and emotional health of the teachers, it is still advised by the researcher that changes in education with or without Coronavirus pandemic should not limit themselves from taking care of their well-being. Health must be the first priority without neglecting the duties and responsibilities of being a teacher. Teachers may consider to prioritize well-being no matter how busy or how many workloads they may have, still healthy mind and body matters most to do the job well.

Keywords: educational change, covid-19 pandemic, teachers' well-being